

Managerial Skills of School Heads and Its Relationship to Teachers' Job Gratification: The Case of Secondary Schools

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managerial skills, job gratification, educational administration intervention

Abstract. This study examined the relationship between school heads' managerial skills and teachers' job gratification within public secondary schools in Eastern Kayapa District. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, empirical data were gathered from seventy-eight (78) teachers through standardized, validated research instruments. Two instruments were utilized: an adapted, 26-item Managerial Skills Questionnaire assessing five domains (technical, human, conceptual, communication, and supervisory skills) and an expert-validated, 40-item researcher-made Job Gratification Questionnaire measuring four key components (job security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community linkage) with an excellent Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.966. Statistical analyses, including mean, and Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson-r), were employed to determine the relationships among variables. Hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 significance level to ensure the validity of the findings. Results indicated that teachers rated their school head's managerial skills as very high as evidenced by an overall grand mean of 3.70. The school heads notably excelled in human, conceptual, technical, and supervisory dimensions though area like communication required improvement. Teachers also demonstrated very high job gratification posting an overall grand mean of 3.61. Specifically, they expressed immense satisfaction particularly in job security, community linkages, and job responsibilities with room for growth in work environment. A significant and positive correlation was established between school head's managerial skills and teachers' job gratification, implying the essential function of effective management in improving teachers' job gratification and maintaining school effectiveness. Based on these findings, the study recommends the development of a structured educational administration intervention program to enhance long-term teacher performance through strengthening managerial skills and sustaining high levels of job gratification.

Introduction

The effectiveness of school leadership continues to be an important issue in today's educational context, especially as schools attempt to adapt to an increase in both organizational and instructional requirements. In this context, the management skills of school leaders such as technical, human, conceptual, communication and supervisory competencies, are key in operating schools efficiently, and improving teacher outcomes. These competencies enable school heads to manage their resources properly, direct instructional practices and develop collaborative environments that support teaching and student learning (Aluan, 2025; Bardissyt, 2021). Recent studies have found that effective leadership positively affects teacher motivation, productivity, and well-being, making management competence a significant contributor to the success of institutions (Capone et al., 2024; Ker et al., 2022). Additional studies have revealed that both psychological and organizational factors will affect teacher job satisfaction. Some examples of these influences are: administrative support; job security; and professional recognition (Cagubcub & Tan, 2025; Espra & Valle, 2025).

In the Philippine educational system, school heads have a critical role in driving policy implementation and delivering good-quality education. Managerial skills have been demonstrated through empirical research to have an impact on the performance and engagement of teachers. For example, according to Abdurahman and Omar (2021), leadership practices affect outcomes for teachers. Additionally, Aluan (2025) stated that effective school leadership must include planning, communication, and supervision. Likewise, Castillo (2025) indicated that strong managerial leadership will positively affect the performance of a teacher. However, challenges presented by limited resources, heavy workloads, and the diversity of the schools will detract from the ability of a school leader to translate their leadership practices into a teacher's positive working conditions (Dulog, 2024). In addition, the job satisfaction of Filipino teachers will be impacted by a variety of factors including organizational commitment and administrative support, emphasizing the need for effective leaders who respond to both the professional and personal needs of their teachers (Cagubcub & Tan, 2025; Espra & Valle, 2025).

In geographically isolated areas, such as the Eastern Kayapa District, the challenges faced by schools are compounded by issues of school accessibility and a lack of resources. Therefore, in such contexts, school heads must demonstrate effective management abilities that will allow them to continue to operate their schools and provide continued support to teachers that may experience a sense of professional isolation (Gamala & Marpa, 2022). Teachers that are in remote areas must depend on the support of their leaders, as this affects their sense of belonging and commitment to their profession (As-il, 2024). Furthermore, collaboration between schools and the community is an important factor in sustaining the level of educational quality (Mandolado & Ancho, 2023).

Existing studies have focused almost entirely on the correlation of managerial skills to teach job satisfaction, especially in rural areas. However, few studies if any, have considered how intrinsic factors of fulfillment and recognition impact teacher job satisfaction. Therefore, this research aimed to close the gap by examining the correlation between the managerial skills of school heads and teachers' level of job satisfaction at schools located in the Eastern District of Kayapa, in order to gain a better understanding of how improved leadership practices can maximize both teacher and student success.

Research Questions

This study determined the relationship of school heads' managerial skills and teachers' job gratification among secondary schools in Eastern Kayapa District. Specifically, it answered the following specific questions:

1. What is the perception of public secondary school teachers in Eastern Kayapa District of the managerial skills of their School Head along the dimensions of technical, human, conceptual, communication, and supervisory skills?
2. What is the respondent's perception on their job gratification along the dimensions of job security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community linkage?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived managerial skills of school head and teachers' job gratification?

Null Hypothesis

The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the managerial skills of school heads and job gratification of teachers was tested in the study.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design to examine the relationship between the managerial skills of school leaders and the job satisfaction of teachers using a descriptive-correlational research method. This research design allows researchers to define the strength and direction of the association between variables, without the manipulation of those variables.

Creswell's (2023) defines quantitative research as research that consists of collecting and analyzing numerical data to objectively measure variables in order to establish statistically valid relationships or correlations between the variable. It uses structured instruments to collect data and applies appropriate statistical techniques to produce reliable, generalizable results."

Data for this study were obtained through the use of a structured questionnaire and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The descriptive-correlational research design allowed the researcher to describe existing conditions and examine the relationship between the managerial skills of school leaders and the job satisfaction of school employees within a specific population. By analyzing the data using statistics, the researcher was able to minimize subjective bias and provide an objective basis for interpreting the findings, thereby producing credible and evidence-based conclusions.

Figure No. 1. Conceptual Framework illustrating the independent and dependent variables of the study

The first box illustrates the dimensions of managerial skills of the school head including technical skills, human skills, conceptual skills, communication skills, and supervisory skills. These components represent the ability of the school head in managing its people, which is essential for the success of an organization.

The second box highlights the dimensions of teachers' job gratification which encompasses job security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community linkage. These components are crucial in determining the productivity and commitment of the public secondary school teachers in Eastern Kayapa District. An arrow connects the two boxes, illustrating the hypothesized link between managerial skills of school head and teachers' job gratification.

This paradigm effectively captures the interrelationships between the managerial skills of school heads and teachers' job gratification that will serve as basis in developing an educational administration intervention entitled "Bridging the Gap: Enhancing Communication Skills and Work Environment for Exceptional Teacher Performance". This training design aims to improve teachers' performance through strengthening school heads' managerial skills and sustaining high levels of job gratification.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. Respondent's Perception of the Managerial Skills of their School Head Along Technical, Human, Conceptual, Communication, and Supervisory Skills

Managerial Skill Dimension	Mean	Qualitative Description
Technical	3.71	Very High
Human	3.73	Very High
Conceptual	3.72	Very High
Communication	3.66	Very High
Supervisory	3.68	Very High
Grand Mean	3.70	Very High

Table 1-Mean and Qualitative Description of the Respondents' Perception of the Managerial Skills of the School Head (n=78)

Data in table 1 indicate that teachers perceive the managerial skills of the school heads as very high, as reflected by the grand mean of 3.70. This implies that school heads consistently manage the operating functions of a school competently, leads the school effectively, and creates a positive work environment for employees. Hence, the level of school leader competency positively influences the way teachers are able to organize their work and receive professional support, thereby impacting their level of job gratification. In support of this finding, Abdurahman and Omar (2021) indicated that effective school leadership practices enhance the experience of teaching; thus, the school leader's management skills are essential to providing an enjoyable and successful working environment for teachers. Further, Gamala and Marpa (2022) indicated that school leaders who demonstrate strong management skills have a significant impact on creating an environment that is conducive to positive attitudes and professional satisfaction among all staff members.

In terms of specific dimensions, human skills emerged as the highest-rated area, with a mean of 3.73. This demonstrates how strong an educational leader can be at establishing positive interpersonal relationships with teachers while providing opportunities for collaboration between staff members and establishing a culture of mutual respect among them. The importance of human skill and relational leadership in an organization like schools is a reflection of the need to build trust, support, and interact with each other to create an environment that fosters both the morale of teachers and their performance. This is consistent with the findings of Khan et al. (2023) that the human skills of the school leaders have a significant impact on the job satisfaction of teachers through a positive school climate. When teachers perceive their school heads as being accessible and supportive, they are more likely to believe that they are appreciated and fulfilled in their work and therefore to be more gratified in their job.

On the other hand, communication skills received the lowest mean of 3.66, although it still falls within the very high qualitative description. This suggests that while the present communication systems function effectively for the most part, they can be enhanced in terms of clarity, consistency, and the ability to share information openly. Communication is an essential component of a school manager's competence since it facilitates improved alignment between individuals, reduces uncertainty, and supports effective collaboration among individuals within an organization. Dulong (2024) indicates that school administrators must communicate effectively with their staff about policies and expectations as well as providing constructive feedback if they are to be successful in today's complex educational environment. Improving how communication may also help teachers to develop a greater sense of belonging and trust as well as increase their overall work satisfaction. Therefore, these findings indicate that school heads have a strong and well-developed managerial skill-set, with one of the greatest strengths with the human skills and an area for growth on the communication skills. These results provide further support for the argument that effective and balanced leadership helps to create a positive work environment and increase job gratification among teachers, and that the school heads managerial competencies greatly impact the teachers' performance and professional experiences positively.

Problem 2. Respondent's Perception of their Job Gratification Along Job Security, Work Environment, Job Responsibilities, and Community Linkages

Job Gratification Dimension	Mean	Qualitative Description
Job Security	3.64	Very High
Work Environment	3.58	Very High
Job Responsibilities	3.59	Very High
Community Linkages	3.62	Very High
Grand Mean	3.61	Very High

Table 2-Mean and Qualitative Description of the Respondents' Perceptions of their Gratification (n=78)

The result in Table 2 indicates that teachers experience a very high level of job gratification, as reflected by the grand mean of 3.61. This implies that job gratification is very satisfying to the teachers due to their level of fulfillment, job satisfaction, and positive levels of engagement at work, all of which have an impact on their professional identity. The results indicating high levels of job satisfaction also indicate how educated employees view their position and the significance, continuity, and support of their job will ultimately lead to higher job quality. This finding is consistent with the study of Espra and Valle (2025) who found that professional and personal commitment to their roles as teachers and therefore to their jobs was influenced by job satisfaction levels and therefore would lead to higher commitment to their jobs and ongoing job engagement. Additionally, Montuori and associates (2021) identified that the workplace practices and attitudes of employees have a major impact on the level of job satisfaction at work and overall could impact the level of job satisfaction at work itself.

To note, job security obtained the highest mean (3.64), indicating that teachers feel stable and assured in their employment. This shows that teachers have a sense of safety and security when it comes to their employment. It also indicates that

schools provide teachers with a sense of job continuity, security and confidence, which helps contribute to providing teachers with continuity and confidence in their work habits. Consequently, having a secured job will allow teachers to create positive work attitudes, commit to their job and invest their time and effort into their work responsibilities (Ibrahim, 2025). Additionally, when teachers are working under secure conditions and do not need to worry about being employed, they are able to devote their full attention to their teaching responsibilities, resulting in an overall higher degree of satisfaction.

On the other hand, work environment received the lowest mean of 3.58, although it still falls within the very high category. This suggests that although many teachers express positive rating towards their workplace setting, it appears some of the elements that comprise a teacher's work environment including physical attributes, the extent of resources needed to conduct one's daily duties, and the quality of relationships that exist among teachers may still require attention or enhancement. The work place is a significant element impacting how effectively teachers are able to cope with their daily responsibilities, and to determine their overall level of job satisfaction. According to Ker et al. (2022), the quality of one's work environment is an important predictor of teacher job satisfaction. Further, they stressed the value of working in an environment that provides ample support, and all the resources that are required to perform optimally within the workplace. Also, Diagne (2023) claimed that administrative support, collaborative relationships with co-workers, and levels of autonomy afforded to teachers as they relate to teacher quality of life. By enhancing these elements, a teacher's overall job satisfaction may improve to levels higher than can be achieved through other elements.

Hence, teaching was found to be very rewarding with job security being their greatest asset. However, there is room for improvement in other aspects of the work environment. This indicates that keeping stable working conditions for teachers and developing ways to improve those conditions are both crucial to maintaining and increasing teachers' feelings of fulfillment from work.

Problem 3. Significant Relationship Between the Managerial Skills of the School Head and Job Gratification of Teachers

Variables Correlated	Computed r-value	Critical r-value	p-value	Remarks
Technical skills and Job Gratification	0.335	0.2227	0.003	Significant
Human skills and Job Gratification	0.499	0.2227	0.000	Significant
Conceptual skills and Job Gratification	0.429	0.2227	0.000	Significant
Communication and skills and Job Gratification	0.383	0.2227	0.001	Significant
Supervisory skills and Job Gratification	0.459	0.2227	0.000	Significant
Overall Managerial Skills and Job Gratification	0.468	0.2227	0.000	Significant

Table 3-Summary of Correlation Between School Head's Managerial Skills and Teachers' Job Gratification

Table 3 reveals a significant relationship between the school head's managerial skills and teachers' job gratification, as indicated by the computed r-value of 0.468, which is higher than the critical value of 0.2227 and supported by a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that the increase in managerial capacity of the school administrator, the level of job satisfaction for the teacher will also increase. It follows then, that strong leadership contributes to the overall experience of the teacher at work and the resulting accomplishments and level of contentment that a teacher has at work. This is in agreement with the findings of Abdurahman & Omar (2021) and Gamala & Marpa (2022), who both concluded that high-quality leadership significantly contributes to the success of the teacher and that the managerial capacity of the leader can influence the culture of the school and therefore the attitudes of teachers.

Human skills exhibited the strongest relationship with job gratification, with an r-value of 0.499. Teachers feel fulfilled by factors such as their social connections, empathy, and the communication of their school heads. Further, school heads with high levels of interpersonal skills create a more cooperative and supportive working environment, building trust, respect, and motivation among teachers with whom they work. This finding supports the finding reported by Khan et al. (2023) that school heads' human skills significantly improve the work climate in schools, which directly impacts teachers' job satisfaction. In addition, the work climate provides a positive emotional climate and increases teachers' commitment to their work and ultimately positively influences job satisfaction.

On the other hand, technical skills showed the weakest relationship with job gratification, with an r-value of 0.335, although it remains statistically significant. The findings of the data indicate that although teachers do believe that they are competent in managing the technical aspects of their jobs, they are less likely to feel fulfilled by being competent in the relational aspects of their jobs. When evaluating whether they are satisfied with their jobs, teachers tend to weigh the importance of relational and supportive leadership more than they do the importance that purely administrative efficiency

has on their overall job satisfaction. On the other hand, the existence of technical competence confirms that a teacher will have both proper management of job tasks and systems in order to create a consistently structured and stable work place. Aluqain (2025) and Castillo (2025) also support the conclusion that a managerial competency is important for a candidate in today's managerial field and that all study results are valid.

Overall, all aspects of managerial competency are strongly correlated with the level of job gratification of teachers. However, human skills have a higher correlation than technical skills with regards to level of job gratification. The implications of these findings show how valuable balanced leadership can be, both personal and managerial skill sets are extremely important in creating a productive working environment and increasing the overall level of job satisfaction of the entire teaching staff.

School leadership has a significant impact on teachers' job satisfaction. When indicating a link between leadership style and teacher satisfaction, the research identified a statistically significant relationship between all areas of manager's skill and teacher satisfaction. Therefore, any improvement in the school leader's managerial skills will directly improve teacher satisfaction. This again supports the notion that leadership is one of the many key factors for ensuring a positive school culture and environment.

An area of research where the school's human skills appear to be the strongest is that of relational leadership, where the teacher values social relationships or social supports from the school leader. Thus, using relational or emotional forms of leadership as a school head rather than a solely technical or administrative form of leadership has the greatest influence on a teacher's sense of satisfaction. All of the technical, conceptual, communicating and supervising skills needed by school heads are essential to support a strong foundation for the operations of the organization and to make the organization efficient.

The lower rating of communication skills, while still rated very highly, suggests an opportunity for enhancement related to the clarity, quantity, and consistency of information shared between the school leader and teachers. Developing communication practices will serve to build trust; foster collaboration; and strengthen the alignment of the school leaders with the teachers.

A high degree of overall job gratification, mainly relating to job security, shows that teachers feel they work in stable and nurturing work environments where they are encouraged to remain as committed teachers. Even with this high level of job satisfaction, teachers reported that the different characteristics of their work environment comprise the lowest score, as they believe their current physical conditions, resources, as well as the overall dynamics of the workplace, need improvement.

All of the above evidence points toward the conclusion that different forms of effective and balanced leadership will establish a more positive climate as a professional workplace for teachers, contribute to the improvement of teacher job satisfaction and support continued development of effective schools.

Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the findings, school heads of secondary schools in Eastern Kayapa District have developed solid management capabilities across five areas (human, conceptual, technical, communication, and supervision) that have been confirmed by teachers. In addition, teachers reported a high level of job gratification work environment, job responsibilities, and community linkages. Lastly, results indicated a significant and positive correlation between the managerial skills of school heads and job gratification of teachers, suggesting that as school heads' leadership skills increases, the level of teacher gratification also increases.

Therefore, it is recommended that school heads improve their supervisory and communication abilities using continuous leadership training, mentoring, and reflective practices to enhance teacher performance and motivation. In addition, schools may provide positive work environments with well-defined roles to positively influence teacher motivation and gratification. Finally, schools are encouraged to develop skills-based professional development programs that focus on employee engagement and job satisfaction, in order to continue delivering quality teaching. Additionally, school heads and supervisors may create initiatives that promote the development of effective instructional supervision, leadership development, and positive communication skills. Finally, future researchers may conduct replication studies in other areas to confirm the findings of this study and broaden their application, as well as look at this topic through qualitative methodologies or utilizing different variables, in order to gain new information about managerial skills and how they impact the satisfaction of teachers with their jobs.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

No new data were created or analyzed during this study.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.